

Hydrogen Bonding Interaction of Parathion with Fluoroalcohols and Thioalcohols

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The equilibrium constants and enthalpy changes of the 1:1 hydrogen bonded complexes of parathion with different fluoroalcohols and different thioalcohols have been estimated from the $\pi-\pi^*$ red shift and the optical density measurements. No correlation could be achieved between the stability constant for hydrogen bond formation and the acidity of the fluoroalcohols and the thioalcohols. By measure of the equilibrium constant, an alcohol is always a better proton donor than the corresponding thioalcohol.

INTERMOLECULAR hydrogen bond formation changes many of the spectral behaviours of the molecules. Systematic attempts have been made to investigate the effect of chemical nature of the proton donors on the stability of the hydrogen bonded complexes. The anomaly in solvent effect on the electronic spectra of parathion which occurs frequently when a polar substance is used as solvent, as observed by Higgs¹ as well as by Hirt and Gislard², may be interpreted in terms of hydrogen-bonding effect. The intermolecular hydrogen bonding properties of ordinary alcohols have been studied in details³⁻⁸ with little information for those of fluoroalcohols⁹⁻¹¹ and thioalcohols¹²⁻¹⁴. Fluoroalcohols are much more acidic than the ordinary alcohols. A possible explanation for the abnormal acidities of the fluoroalcohols is the formation of strong intramolecular hydrogen bond. Dimerization of thiols takes place at high concentration and low temperature¹⁵. Self-association of thiols is weak. The investigation of the hydrogen bonding interaction involving π electrons as base is of interest with increasing evidence of hydrogen bond formation of olefins and aromatics¹⁶⁻²⁰ as proton acceptors with the compound having proton donating capacity leading to important observation and conclusions.

The acid-like behaviour of some fluoroalcohols and thioalcohols has been utilised in the present work to study the interaction between several fluoroalcohols and thioalcohols as proton donors and parathion as proton acceptor in carbon tetrachloride as solvent. We report herein some quantitative results of the O-H- π and S-H- π hydrogen bonding. We have utilized Nagakura and Baba's²¹ suggestion that $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of organic molecules with suitable chromophores undergoes red shift in proton donor solvents due to solute-solvent hydrogen bonding interaction and also that quantitative estimations of such interactions could

be made by spectral measurements at the shifted peak. Bready and Kasha's method as modified by Chandra and Basu has been followed in the present investigation in calculating the stability constant of the hydrogen bonded complexes. Uptil now no definite composition of the hydrogen bonded complexes of proton donors like fluoroalcohols and thioalcohols with parathion has been reported.

Experimental

Parathion was obtained as gift sample from Bayer India Limited. This was steam-distilled and extracted with *n*-hexane from the distillate. The *n*-hexane extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was evaporated. The solutions were then made in carbon tetrachloride. The non-hydrogen bonding solvent was Merck's carbon tetrachloride which was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and distilled before use. Trifluoroethanol was kindly supplied by Pennsalt Chemical Corporation. Pentafluoropropanol, heptafluorobutanol and pentadecafluorooctanol were obtained as gift samples from Peninsular Chemical Research Inc. Other fluoroalcohols, octafluoropentanol and decafluoroheptanol were obtained as gift sample from E. I. Du Pont de Namours and Co. The thioalcohols were kindly supplied by Eastman Organic Chemical, N.Y. All these compounds were obtained in highly purified form and used as such.

The solutions were made gravimetrically and the spectral measurements were taken with freshly prepared solutions on a Hilger uv-speck spectrophotometer using 1 cm stoppered quartz cells at different temperatures (a temperature, constant within $\pm 0.5^\circ$, being maintained by circulating water through the cell holder).

Sufficient increase of fluoroalcohol concentration in a solution of parathion shifted the $\pi-\pi^*$ band

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of the later to higher wave length side (red shift). Fig. 1 shows how the $\pi-\pi^*$ band of parathion shifted on increasing the concentration of ethane thiol. The optical density measurements were made on carbon tetrachloride solution of parathion with varying concentration of the fluoroalcohols and the thioalcohols at the shifted peak.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of parathion in 0 (I), 0.987 M (II), 1.974 M (III), and 2.961 (IV) of ethanethiol in carbon tetrachloride. Concentration of parathion is $5 \times 10^{-5} M$ in all cases.

The physico-chemical basis of the method of calculating the stability constant of the hydrogen bonded complexes, as described previously^{22,23}, leads to the equation

$$\frac{[A]}{(\bar{\epsilon} - \epsilon_0)} = \frac{1}{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_0) K} + \frac{[A]}{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_0)} \quad \dots (1)$$

where [A] is the concentration of the proton donor. Other symbols carry the same significance as described.

From the slope and the intercept of the linear plot of $[A]/(\bar{\epsilon} - \epsilon_0)$ vs [A], the equilibrium constant K can be evaluated (Fig. 2). The equation (1) was derived under the assumptions (a) the concentration of the hydrogen bonded proton acceptor is negligibly small compared with that of the proton donor and (b) the proton donor and the proton

Fig. 2. Plots of $[A]/\bar{\epsilon} - \epsilon_0$ vs [A] for all fluoro alcohol-parathion system. [Subscripts under C represents the no. of carbon atoms in the fluoro alcohols].

acceptor interact one for one. These two assumptions seem to be satisfied for the solutions used in the present investigations. The enthalpy change ($-\Delta H$) of hydrogen bond formation between the alcohols and parathion was estimated from the variations of equilibrium constant with temperature and was calculated from the slope of the plots of $\log K$ against $1/T$ (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. (I) 2-Mercaptoethanol, (II) Ethanethiol, (III) Propanethiol, (IV) Butanethiol, (V) Pentanethiol and (VI) Heptanethiol.

Results and Discussion

Tables 1 and 2 summarize the values of the

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS AND ENTHALPY CHANGES OF HYDROGEN BONDED COMPLEXES BETWEEN PARATHION AND FLUOROALCOHOLS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Shifted peak nm	Concn. of proton donor M/L	Temp. °C	Equilibrium constant M^{-1}	$-\Delta H$ K cal/mole	pKa Water
Concn. of parathion = $5 \times 10^{-5} M$; Peak of non-complexed parathion 268 nm					
Trifluoroethanol-parathion complex					
275	0.052-0.416	25	0.498 ± 0.022	6.06 ± 0.08	11.31
		35	0.989 ± 0.043		
		45	0.263 ± 0.033		
Pentafluoropropanol-parathion complex					
274	0.039-0.312	25	0.364 ± 0.048	5.61 ± 0.16	11.31
		35	0.303 ± 0.043		
		45	0.209 ± 0.002		
Heptafluorobutanol-parathion complex					
273	0.078-0.624	25	0.427 ± 0.02	5.89 ± 0.46	—
		35	0.331 ± 0.042		
		45	0.244 ± 0.017		
Octafluoropentanol-parathion complex					
273	0.031-0.248	25	0.325 ± 0.032	5.79 ± 0.51	11.84
		35	0.225 ± 0.018		
		45	0.170 ± 0.006		
Decafluoroheptanol-parathion complex					
272	0.035-0.280	25	0.263 ± 0.025	5.48 ± 0.10	11.33
		35	0.214 ± 0.030		
		45	0.151 ± 0.008		
Pentadecafluorooctanol-parathion complex					
272	0.027-0.216	25	0.228 ± 0.012	5.23 ± 0.20	—
		35	0.158 ± 0.031		
		45	0.137 ± 0.019		

TABLE 2—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT AND ENTHALPY CHANGES OF HYDROGEN BONDED COMPLEXES BETWEEN PARATHION AND THIOLS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE

Concn. of parathion = 5×10^{-5} ;
Peak of non-complexed parathion 269 nm

Shifted peak nm	Temp. °C	Equilibrium constant M^{-1}	$-\Delta H$ K cal/mole	pKa in Water
2-Mercaptoethanol-parathion complex				
273	25	0.258 ± 0.015	4.99	9.72
	35	0.223 ± 0.003		
	45	0.161 ± 0.016		
Ethanethiol-parathion complex				
273	25	0.234 ± 0.036	4.91	10.60
	35	0.169 ± 0.010		
	45	0.136 ± 0.004		
Propanethiol-parathion complex				
272	25	0.201 ± 0.015	4.67	10.65
	35	0.128 ± 0.009		
	45	0.114 ± 0.027		
Butanethiol-parathion complex				
272	25	0.168 ± 0.001	4.59	10.66
	35	0.119 ± 0.013		
	45	0.095 ± 0.029		
Pentanethiol-parathion complex				
272	25	0.139 ± 0.014	4.49	10.70
	35	0.109 ± 0.032		
	45	0.079 ± 0.006		
Heptanethiol-parathion complex				
271	25	0.104 ± 0.002	4.08	10.75
	35	0.091 ± 0.028		
	45	0.064 ± 0.003		

equilibrium constants and enthalpy changes of the hydrogen bonded complex between parathion and different alcohols. The values of equilibrium constant for a given system are constant within 5%. We have also found isobestic points in the $\pi-\pi^*$ band of parathion in carbontetrachloride fluoroalcohols and carbontetrachloride thioalcohols system. This indicates the existence of equilibrium between the hydrogen bonded and free species of the solute.

The spectral shifts in the $\pi-\pi^*$ band of parathion are associated with the hydrogen bond formations through the hydroxyl group of the fluoroalcohols and the sulfhydryl ($-\text{SH}$) group of the thioalcohols with the π -electron system of the benzene ring of parathion leading to $\text{OH}-\pi$ and $\text{SH}-\pi$ interaction. All the plots of $[A]/(\epsilon-\epsilon_0)$ vs $[A]$ were linear providing evidence for 1:1 hydrogen bonded complex formation between the alcohols and parathion. Though the fluoroalcohols as well as the thioalcohols are self-associated at low temperature and specially at high concentration it is evident from the equilibrium constant values shown in Tables 1 and 2 that at the experimental concentration and temperature intermolecular hydrogen bonding of the alcohols with parathion is also considerable. The ability of these fluoroalcohols and the thiols to form 1:1 complexes further support the hydrogen bonding capabilities of these alcohols with parathion.

Tables 1 and 2 show that the pKa values of the fluoroalcohols do not differ very much from each other whereas there is a marked difference in stability constant values. Therefore, though a rudimentary kind of parallelism can be discerned, evidently no correlation can be drawn between the equilibrium constant values with the acidic strength of these fluoroalcohols. Such was also the observation for the thioalcohols under investigation. Thus, the factors which are responsible for acidity in water may not be the same or similar in hydrogen bond formation.

A comparison of the equilibrium constant values of some analogous proton donors (ethyl alcohol, propyl alcohol and butyl alcohol) reported in an earlier communication^{2,4} with those of corresponding thioalcohol shows that the equilibrium constant values are smaller in the cases of the thiols. Therefore, by measure of equilibrium constant values an alcohol is always a better proton donor than the corresponding thioalcohol.

The enthalpy changes of hydrogen bond formation follows the order: trifluoroethanol > heptafluorobutanol > octafluoropentanol > pentafluoropropanol > decafluoroheptanol > pentadecafluorooctanol for the fluoroalcohol-parathion systems and the order: 2-mercaptoethanol > ethanethiol > propanethiol > butanethiol > pentanethiol > heptanethiol for the thiol-parathion system. Since at the experimental concentration and temperature self-association of the fluoroalcohols and of the thiols may be neglected, it is quite likely that the calculated hydrogen bond energies do represent the energy of the hydrogen bond. In case we are interested only in the relative values, comparison of the values for a series of fluoroalcohols as well as for the thioalcohols will also probably be valid.

The present investigation provides valuable information for the hydrogen bonding properties of parathion which becomes much beneficial to the forensic toxicologists in regard to detection and estimation of this compound.

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